

LINK BETWEEN THE CONDUCT AS STRATEGIES AND TRAINING OF BUSINESS

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Abstract:

Industrial systems have received attention in recent years to explain the behavior of companies from a broad perspective, integrating business strategy with structure. Collaborative network is a model that explains the structure of industrial systems to analyze interactions through methods that combine economic with social elements. This paper discusses how partnership strategies of firms derived from external forces to the organization, and implemented by behaviors, shapes the structure, identity and governance of local business networks around a common goal, and highlights the role of agents in the business process evolution of the formalization of networks.

Keywords: Competitiveness, Collaboration, Strategy, Collaborative Enterprise networks

JEL: P130, P170, D850, L140, L220, L230, L240

Resumen

Los sistemas industriales han recibido atención en los últimos años para explicar el comportamiento de las empresas desde una perspectiva ampliada, integrando asuntos de estrategia con estructura. Las redes de empresas constituyen un modelo que explica la estructura de los sistemas industriales que permite analizar las interacciones mediante métodos que combinan elementos económicos y sociales. El presente trabajo trata de cómo las estrategias de colaboración de las empresas, derivados de fuerzas externas a la organización, y aplicadas mediante conductas, moldean la estructura, identidad y gobernanza de las redes empresariales locales en torno a un objetivo común, y destaca el rol de los agentes de las empresas en el proceso de formalización de las redes.

Palabras clave: Competitividad, colaboración, estrategia, redes empresariales.

1. Introduction

The literature on strategy generally addresses the problem of how to improve organizational performance in a competitive environment. Empirical evidence suggests that business strategy improves financial performance (Bloom, Genakos, Sadun, & Van Renee, 2012). But this principle applies to SME's?; and how this principle is applied to the competitiveness of regions, tourist destinations, and industrial groupings? Is it the same to speak of competitiveness and sustainability in a large company with global projection of a collection of SME's related? What are the differences and similarities between the structures of large enterprises with the structures of industrial systems of SME's? And more importantly, how partnerships between companies are developed in an industrial system to be competitive or sustainable?

The formation of business networks has been a topic increasingly in recent years, and is the subject of international and national agenda. The negotiation of partnership and collaboration has become new ways of growth and expansion ... Instead of competing and pushing each other out of the market, it is better to collaborate (Clegg, Kornberger, & Pitsis, 2011, p. 381). With the increasing globalization, companies seek mechanisms to compete and survive a rapidly changing industrial activity and changes in the characteristics of demand (United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2008). Given these challenges, linking

businesses (networking) is an activity that accounts as an alternative for small and medium businesses (Sakai, 2002).

In the new economy, characterized by the ability to generate knowledge and process information, and globalization, enterprise network becomes the heart of the new form of economic organization (Castells, 2000). From the point of view of ONUDI (1999), individual SME's could achieve to solve problems related to their size and improve their competitive position through networking, from the horizontal and vertical cooperation, and introduces the concepts of "networks" "clusters" and "linkage" or "networking", which form the basis internationally.

ONUDI mentioned that there has been other evidence where inter-firm cooperation does not always arise spontaneously, and that the most important factors that promote the formation include: a) high transaction costs that force the formation of a network identity partners; b) market imperfections that require development of links for the exchange of information and innovation; c) the high risk of opportunism where the legal framework does not provide conditions for the joint venture.

In this context, UNIDO (2008) mentions that the biggest obstacle in cluster development is often a lack of coordination, consistency and relevance rather than absence of support services available to businesses ... This implies that, in many instances, capacity building does not necessarily mean the creation of a new institution, but the creation of networking that helps to bridge the gap between supply and demand. There is a lot of evidence on productive integration in different continents (Lopez Cerdan Ripoll, 2003). They emphasize in this regard the experiences of Japanese Keiretsu (Camarinha Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2011), and Italian export consortia (Minervini, 2014, p. 260).

In the case of Mexico, it has extensive experience in business cooperation, networking, clusters and other forms of association. The most notable effort is the program of integrating companies (Rodríguez & Fernández Monroy Chalet, 2008), although there are other programs implemented by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the Supplier Development Program of Nacional Financiera (NAFIN) and agency programs Trusts in Relation to Agriculture (Fideicomisos Instituidos en Relación con la Agricultura, FIRA) (López Cerdan Ripoll, 2003). In the National Development Plan 2013-2028 various elements relating to the integration of productive chains (Presidencia de la República, 2013) are included.

2. Development

A. Concept of business networks

Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2012) state that there is a tendency in the industry and services to seek synergies through participation in networks ... in both industrial and service collaboration networks have existed for a long time. Becerra (2008) mentions that the study on production systems together has had more growth than on companies as particular units, especially the analysis concerning entrepreneurial companies and their configurations have. Becerra said about the importance of analysis of phenomena associated with the emergence and development of enterprises within a system of relationships with external agents (stakeholders), which can affect the behavior of the company.

In particular, the author mentioned the establishment of business relations with their direct competitors, suppliers, customers, governments and other local or regional players, enabling them to develop sources of competitive advantage, in particular small and medium business. Becerra presents networks as mechanisms or strategies of integration and coordination of different agents, with a common goal; it emphasizes that networks are a type of structure that can take different forms, sizes and geographic scope.

Brunet and Galeana (2004) described the scheme as flexible network structures within an emerging paradigm that enables organizations to adapt quickly. Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2012) define the connection (networking) as a process of communication and information exchange among the participants for mutual benefit, though not necessarily involves a common purpose or structure. A coordinated networking (Coordinated networking) is a process that adds alignment or alteration of activities to achieve results more efficiently.

The study of networks through the theory of social capital is focused by relational structural dimensions with sub-dimensions of cohesion and structural holes, quoting Granovetter (1992), Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998)

and resources, but few research has simultaneously considered the distinct dimensions of social capital (Casanueva Rocha Castro Abancéns, & Galan Gonzalez, 2010). In this work the relationship between the behavior of the agents with the structure and relationships of the networks will be analyzed.

B. Concept of strategy

Business strategy has been analyzed from four complementary approaches: as a position in an industry based on differentiation (Porter, 1996); based capabilities and dynamic VRIO resources (Barney, 1991); as access to critical resources based on legitimacy, reputation, influence and networks (Peng, Li Sun, Pnkham, & Chen, 2009); and as an extended cognition and information management for strategic decision making (Gavetti, 2012).

The best known approach (Porter, 1996), describes the strategy of an organization as the configuration of various elements of the organization to achieve a condition of differentiation, which is a way to offer attractive products and services in a market with such an approach that captures greater customer value than the competition. In the case of resource-based theory (Barney, 1991), the strategy is described as the development of dynamic capabilities from valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and available for the operation of the organization resources. The institutional approach (Peng et al., 2009), mentions that the strategy is to obtain competitive advantages from the development of relations in networking from the legitimacy and prestige of the organization.

Finally, Gavetti (2012) describes the strategy as the product of a combination of psychological phenomena, particularly cognition of new opportunities and transforming them into behaviors that allow cognition into action implement that produce competitive advantages. This approach is consistent with theories of organizational learning, especially learning the proposal as an adaptation to the environment in which the organization faces (Clegg, Kornberger, & Pitsis, 2011, p. 379).

In short, these approaches focus on one direction: competition. Therefore, it is propose the following criticism:

Review 1: Behavioral approach to competition alone.

When analyzing competitive strategies systemically, at a micro level, firms compete for portions of the local market; but in a meso level, companies need to work together to adopt a defensive position against companies operating at a meta level competing by portions for global market (Potes Nieto, 2007; Dawar & Frost, 1999).

C. Collaborative strategy concept

Specifically, collaborative strategies are a particular kind of strategy identified in the literature (Thompson Jr., Strickland III, & Gamble, 2008): Companies of all industries in the world decided to form strategic alliances and partnerships to complement their own strategic initiatives and strengthen their competitiveness in domestic and international markets. This did not happen in the past, as most companies prefer to act on their own, confident that they already had, or they could be bought separately, resources and skills necessary to succeed in their markets.

But globalization of the world economy, revolutionary advances in broad fronts of technology and new opportunities in Asia, Latin America and Europe, whose domestic markets are in the process of opening, deregulation and / or constant privatization have made strategic partnerships of either class integral parts of competition in a wide geographic scale.

The cooperation strategy or collaboration is that in which two or more companies work together to achieve a common goal (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2009, p. 268). Derived from this approach in the strategy, the formation of networks makes sense. A link is formal when two or more organizations agree to coordinate their interdependencies directly to reduce uncertainty. The more formal a link, the greater the direct coordination and the likelihood of that are based on an explicit agreement, or involve some common ownership between organizations. The more casual is a link, more indirect or inaccurate is the method of coordination, and more likely that this is based on an implicit or tacit agreement (Jones, 2008, p. 67).

Thompson, Strickland and Gamble (2008, p. 163) mention that relations between the partners in a strategic alliance could be by contract or only collaboration. Also mention that an alliance in this regard consists of five factors:

- 1) Pursue an important goal
- 2) Help to build, sustain or increase a core competency or competitive advantage.
- 3) Helping to block a competitive threat.
- 4) Helping to open major new business opportunities.
- 5) Reduce risks and uncertainties.

As a result, the strategy of network cooperation is an agreement between several companies in order to form multiple associations that cooperate to achieve shared objectives (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2009, p. 284). Internationally, this convention has produced different structures (Figure 1). Collaborative strategies and partnership models are coarse, product integration processes where networking is a phenomenon dependent on the number of partners, the objective of the association and the size of the partners, among other factors. From these concepts arise the following criticisms:

Review 2: collaboration strategies documented reference to the resulting structure, not (1) a competitive position, (2) relationships, (3) behavior

Review 3: There has not been talk of structure and concept of industrial systems; however, the network constitutes a structure.

D. The relationship between strategy and structure

The relationship between structure and strategy has been documented in the literature comprehensively. An organization is created to achieve some goals. To achieve and support the course set by the organizational mission and operational goals, managers must choose specific strategy and design options of structure to help the organization achieve its purpose and targets within this competitive environment (Daft, 2009, pp. 56-62).

Figure 1: Classification of associative relationships

Source: Badaracco Jr., 1992, p. 130

This relationship initially documented by Chandler (1962), has been studied in countless investigations, sometimes stating that the structure follows strategy, and other reverse. The dominant paradigm is that the structure follows strategy (Carrion Maroto, 2007, p. 388)

E. Networks like structure.

Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2005) propose and in turn introduce the concept of collaborative networks as a general concept to explain the organization of a group of companies that has emerged in recent years, such as virtual networks, outsourcing, among others. These authors analyze the empirical evidence of publications in recent years, and suggest that the study of collaborative networks are a new discipline in science, based on formal theories and models of dynamic networks; graph theory; formal engineering methods; semiotics, regulatory and multi-agent models; network analysis and game theory; temporal and modal logic; metaphors; complexity theory; dynamic ontologies; and more recently computer science models and dynamic distribution groups.

They add that the study of networks, the areas of study include: coordination, information management, information exchange inter-operability, security, communications, contracts, horizontal structures, resource management and infrastructure development. Camarinha and Afsarmanesh added in 2011 than in seeking synergies through participation in networks is a growing trend, although it has existed for a long time. In his analysis, they cite the formation of the Keiretsu in Japan in the recent history in the 1970s and 1980s. In the 1990s the rise of outsourcing from the contributions of Williamson on transaction costs theory and its application to the formation of alliances and distributed production.

In this new contribution, the authors analyze the evolution of the business ecosystem highlighting the rapid reorganization of the links, resulting in network structures that are dynamically reconfigured according to the perceived needs and market opportunities, and introducing the concept of self-organization of these dynamic systems and adaptive processes. In this process, the evidence pointing to the interactions of individuals is important emotionally. From this perspective, leadership, conflict management, negotiation and mediation are introduced to the study of networks elements, highlighting their contributions based on the analysis of social networks.

Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2012) identify the networks as a form of organization, as a form of structure of relationships, among members of an industrial system, and establish a classification of these networks based on the approach to relations (Figure 2). Pedro Pablo Ramos (2008, p. 3) mentions that, big or small, industrial or service companies or cooperatives, enterprises are a network. This network is presented internally between people, processes, activities, knowledge, information, objectives and strategy; and externally with the market, customers, suppliers, and others. He also mentions that this network can be well connected or not.

A traditional organizational chart allows visualizing the lines of communication that in turn allows the proper coordination of resources through the division of labor and specialization hierarchies placing the authority to make decisions. This organization has evolved structurally the companies to include more items.

Figure 2: Examples of collaborative networks.

Source: Camarinha and Afsarmanesh, (2012).

In the circular chart, the traditional structure is smoothed to present an inclusive organizational culture, eliminating the idea of hierarchy, and displaying an image as in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Organizational traditional circular

Source: Authors

However, to identify relationships between people (Hill, 2011, pp. 421-436) created by the activities, processes, equipment and social relations, the structure of the company has a network structure (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Internal Network

Source: Authors

In this sense, (Ramos, 2008, p. 8), the internal network in the company is not invented, but rather discovered, and as discussed below, extends outside the company. The network diagram presents approximately the informal organization underlying the formal organization. The intra-organizational or intra-firm networks correspond to a model of linking structures deployed in different geographical locations, even different countries to collaborate because of ties of ownership as a single owner or group of owners (Cleri, 1999, p. 162; Hill, 2011, pp 398-399). The resulting structure is similar to the network shown in Figure 5, where the business units in different geographical locations have its own network of the town, and by the different integration mechanisms derived from the processes, equipment, knowledge networks and the matrix structure, a series of linkages within the firm or multinational corporation is observed.

Figure 5: Network intra companies with multiple locations
Source: Authors

From the point of view inter-organizational, a network is a diverse group of organizations whose actions are coordinated by contracts and agreements rather than formal hierarchy of authority (Jones, 2008, p. 70). The value chain concept includes setting processes and the structure of the company to transform inputs into outputs (Hill & Jones, Strategic Management, 2009, p. 83). To understand the structure of an industrial system it is used the concept of value network. A value network is a shaped by various participants in the production of goods and services from production to consumption system (Rivas Tovar, 2011, p. 299). This concept is similar to that used by Porter (1987, p. 50)

Figure 6. Network and organizational environment
Source: Hatch, 2006, p. 67.

Analyzing this concept, a complex industrial system is reduced, for analysis, at its most basic component: the relationship between the company and its customers and suppliers (Figure 7). The value chain of the company, as a set of internal processes, has an external source (suppliers) and an external destination (customers), establishing the relationship between basic and most important business organization.

Figure 7. Network basic value

Source: Based on Nalebuff & Brandenburger, 1996, p. 2-3.

In this scheme, the competitors are those who need or receive inputs from the same suppliers, or deliver outputs to the same customers.

Figure 8: Network value with competitors

Source: Based on Nalebuff & Brandenburger, 1996, p. 2-3

From the perspective of the theory of resource dependency, the goal of an organization is to minimize its dependence on other organizations for the provision of scarce resources of its environment (Jones, 2008, pp. 65-67). Therefore, companies should focus simultaneously in two directions:

- 1) Obtain resources from other organizations.
- 2) Respond to the needs and demands of other organizations.

These actions, put in context, will depend on the actions taken by competitors. To the extent that resources are scarce, organizations are competing, while the degree in which there are common goals, cooperate. Thus, to initiate and consolidate activities, companies, or more precisely, members of the organization, learn to compete. If an organization decides to adopt a collaborative model must balance its needs to reduce dependence on resources from loss of autonomy. As a result, an organization seeks to choose inter-organizational strategy that offers the greatest reduction in uncertainty with the least loss of control (Jones, 2008, pág. 67).

Moreover, customers and suppliers not only work with companies that produce the same products or services. There are, at par, other companies in the system that adopt complementary roles or accessories in the structure of the industry. The first type is called by Nalebuff and Brandenburger (1996, p. 23) helper or completer (Figure 9), because it provides value to the network in terms of appealing to customers or suppliers. For example, in tourism, in addition to hotels, restaurants, bars, museums, airlines, among others, form the completer set to generate attractive to tourist destination (industrial system). Partner with complementary possible to develop competitive advantages (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2009, p. 274).

Figure 9: Network value with competitors and complementing agents.
Source: Nalebuff and Brandenburger, 1996, p. 2. 3

Finally, the horizontal analysis, there are other organizations that do not add value, but that their activities support the formation of the structure of the industrial system (Figure 10). These organizations may be part of other industrial systems in the locality are institutions or government agencies.

Figure 10: Network horizontally extended value
Source: Based on Nalebuff & Brandenburger, 1996, p. 2-3

Thus, the integration of horizontal networks corresponds to the formation of alliances between competitors, completer and / or other organizations of the industrial system (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Horizontal integration.
Source: Authors

Starting off again from the basic model (Figure 7) shows that many customers also cater to other customers, indirect customers, except the final consumers and suppliers also use other products and inputs of indirect suppliers. With this approach, the analysis is extended vertically (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Network value vertically extended
 Source: Authors

The concept of vertical integration is defined by the cooperation between organizations at different levels of operation in the production system (Figure 13).

This integration can be promoted by companies making up the network, or led by the client (Figure 14) or supplier (Figure 15). In the case of the networks promoted by the client, are often referred to as supplier development (like the Japanese keiretsu) (Thompson Jr., Strickland III, & Gamble, 2008, pp. 171-175), and generally these customers they are called in Mexico "driving companies" and is related to a process of vertical integration.

Figure 13: Vertical Integration
 Source: Authors

Figure 14: Network customer focused value
 Source: Authors

Figure 17: Network representatives inter organizational.

Source: Authors.

This conceptual structure is consistent with the idea that organizations are open systems created by interactions between members of the company and people from the environment in a dynamic process, where it influences the environment and receives influence from it through these relationships (Chiavenato, 2006, p. 374), and corresponding with the postmodern paradigm (Hatch, 2006, pp. 90-95).

Empirical evidence on the formation of networks in the literature is extensive. Bonomie and Meleán (2007) presented to company networks as a strategy of cooperation between suppliers and distributors in the poultry sector of Zulia, Venezuela. The research analyzed the productive chain, analyzing the production and distribution phases. The methodology was descriptive, from the application of questionnaires and interviews. The paper is, among others, the enterprise network configuration as shown in Figure 18.

The results indicate that the networks as a way of organization in this sector have proliferated in recent decades by a particular feature: organizational flexibility. So it can be concluded that they have allowed the companies analyzed: reducing operating costs, control essential information on the network, coordinate activities, create barriers to entry, and respond together, solidarity and flexibility to the market, among others. Poultry companies analyzed have decentralized their production to go outlining their own networks. This has led them to take cooperation strategies back and forth with suppliers and distributors ensuring the coordination and synchronization of the inputs needed for productive activities or for the timely delivery of products to final consumers.

Figure 18: Business Networking poultry sector of Zulia

Source: Bonomie & Meleán Romero, 2007

The configuration of enterprise networks in the industry involving different types materialize relations, among which can be identified including relations of belonging, exclusivity (information networks triples) and

relationships with other companies (external networks) (Bonnie & Meleán Romero, 2007). Becerra and Alvarez (2011) studied the relationship between the level of training of human resources and linkages between companies within the textile cluster of the city of Manizales, Caldas, Colombia, as determinants of business innovation performance. The result concludes that the training of human resources, the existence of specialized areas, strategic human resource plans and joint actions between companies involving human resources, positively affect business innovation.

Becerra and Serna (2012) presented a study of the relationship of the links in R & D between companies and institutions to innovation within companies in the same textile cluster of the city of Manizales, Colombia. In their study, they mention that innovation and innovation activities (R & D & I) occurring within the company, but beyond are presented in environments where they are located. This environmental aspect is broken down into two perspectives: location and concentration-agglomeration company business (realization of R & D), and transactional aspects (transfer of technical and technological information - TTTI).

The results gave evidence, on the one hand, the limited capacity of enterprises to develop innovations and capabilities of R & D that can be explained by the production structure of the network, composed mainly of micro and small enterprises ... and on the other hand, the data showed a low propensity of enterprises to establish links for joint activities. In contrast, the links between firms to carry out R & D and TTTI direct impact on the innovative capacity of the company, and specifically allow developing the R & D & I in the company, in greater proportion than those that do not develop links with other companies and institutions.

Review 4: The structures of large enterprises and structures of SME's networks are similar

Figure 19: Pyramid of Partnership Development
Source: Porter Lynch, 1995, p. 71

3. Process networking

Porter Lynch (1995, p. 71) proposed a process for forming alliances that part of the existence of driving forces and the strategy of the company. A driving force, which is usually an external factor, becomes the main reason for the creation of an alliance, and becoming the main objective (Thompson Jr., Strickland III, & Gamble, 2008, p 163; Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2009, p. 284). In forming partnerships, Porter Lynch (1995, p. 71) mentions and describes a process led by the driving forces and strategy.

Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2012) presented a new document provides elements to consolidate the terminology database of collaboration networks. In this paper, the authors introduce two fundamental elements on collaborative networks: The lifecycle. According to this model, networks evolve, from its formation to its disappearance.

4. The behavior as an instrument of creation and implementation of the strategy

Ramos (2008) proposes the intra-firm network model as the ratio of management activities with behavior (roles) played by people. Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2011) analyzed the evolution of the business ecosystem highlighting the rapid reorganization of the links, resulting in network structures that are dynamically reconfigured according to the perceived needs and market opportunities, and introducing the concept self-organization of these dynamic systems and adaptive processes.

In this process, the evidence points to the interactions of individuals that is important emotionally. From this perspective, leadership, conflict management, negotiation and mediation are introduced to the study of networks elements, highlighting their contributions based on the analysis of social networks. Camarinha and Afsarmanesh point out that are needed more fundamental research combining aspects of business, power suppliers, barriers to entry, concentration of forms, etc. These are social aspects such as social capital, workforce diversity, issues environmental, etc., and add topics like leadership and its relationship with the network structure and its proximity to the structures and institutions of government.

From the point of view of the behaviorist school administrators work in negotiation situations (Chiavenato, 2006, p. 283), due to differences between the common goals of individual goals. While the behavioral approach is directed towards internal relations in organizations, the principle is applicable in shaping corporate networks, but in terms of horizontality among participants.

The strategy, plans, structure, network, by themselves has no life. Life must be given by the people, with their behaviors. The activity is what adds value and what adds value to the activity is people with their behavior. The behavior is "how" we do what we do. (Ramos, 2008, p. 87) The behaviors, according to Ramos, are a way of implementing the collaborative approach needed to produce results through the formation of the (Ramos, 2008, p. 87) network. Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2012) take as a starting point the difference between cooperation and collaboration. Cooperation defines it as a process that involves not only the exchange of information and adjustment of activities, but also the sharing of resources to achieve objectives compatible. Cooperation is achieved by dividing tasks among participants (Camarinha Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2012).

On the other hand, cooperation is a process in which the entities share information, resources and responsibilities in the planning, implementation and evaluation of program activities to achieve a common goal (Matos & Afsarmanesh Camarinha, 2012). This concept is derived from the Latin *collaborare* which means "working together" and can be seen as a process of shared creation; and a process by which a group of entities mutually are enhancing capabilities. It involves sharing risk, resources, responsibilities and rewards, and if desired, the group may also give an outside observer the image of a joint identity. The collaboration involves the mutual commitment of the participants to solve a problem together, which implies mutual trust and therefore takes time, effort and dedication.

In collaboration, the parties are more closely aligned in the direction of "working together" to achieve the desired outcome, rather than the scope is achieved through the "individualistic" limited participation by contextual factors, such as those imposed by the relationships customer-supplier or sub-contractors. (Camarinha Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2012) Due to the above, the necessary behaviors can be called collaborative work together in this work. In internal networks, the model of Ramos mentioned behaviors such as leadership, equipment, communication, conflict management, customer focus, results orientation, horizontality and innovation.

Figure 20: Model of organizational development of Joan Payeras
Source: Ramos, 2008, p. 88

However, the focus of cooperation between companies is not a subject of recent study. Baderacco (1992) mentions that creating and managing alliances is an unnatural act for many American managers, since intellectual and intuitively believe that firms get along better as citadels (p. 95). Scheel (2008, pp. 226-232) mentions that the participants in an association or cluster have no knowledge at all neither of their relationships, nor believe they have activities or common goals, and aim almost always unique and individual benefits.

This indicates that it is an anti-systemic, reductionist situation and the win-win is unrealistic and unlikely to achieve. Business cooperation is not a natural process: it must be created structures and link flows, systems, styles and goals as "artificial" under a systemic approach, coordinated, expansionist and mutual collaboration, most often strikes the native organizational culture of each of the companies forming the chain.

Figure 21: Diagram of influence of a model of economic integration sector.
Source: Ibarra, 1997, as quoted in Mayenberger Scheel, 2008, p. 2. 3. 4.

In this integration process, a dilemma for the company is present: to compete or to collaborate. Scheel (2008, pp 234-237) describes a model focused on two key variables: the internal rivalry and cooperation capacity (Figure 21). In the integration process, the position of relative advantage of competitors becomes a negative factor for integration, while the capacity of cooperation becomes a positive factor. The result will be influenced by the result in the interaction of these forces. An important variable influencing the result is the clarity of the rules defined by regulations or contracts that will impact decreasing internal rivalry.

As expansion of this model, external forces resulting from globalization will increase the need for cooperation; although this variable is not necessarily related to the ability of cooperation, so the cluster formation is not a necessary consequence ... could, in very bad case, cause the disappearance of the actors. Barcellos, Borella, Peretti and Galelli (2012) identified that aspects of individualism and lack of confidence and trust caused the failure in the networks of cooperation. Their conclusion is that if each member of the network has no internal arrangement - one that begins with the individual - to give up their individuality and their particular goals for some key decisions that provide important collective benefits, the network is permanently exposed and vulnerable to failure. This conclusion leads to the need for further research on the relationship of the behavior of the members of the network with the structure, objectives, organization and government.

In this sense, the concept of "driving force" introduced by Porter Lynch is important for the formation of enterprise networks because the owners and directors of these will be unwilling to create shared and collaborative structures in the absence of these factors. Success in the formation of the network depends on seven behavioral factors (Thompson Jr., Strickland III, & Gamble, 2008) (Hill & Jones, Strategic Management, 2009, pp 293-298.)

- 1) To elect the partners. A good partner should have the power and resources, and in particular must share the vision of the purpose of the collaboration and ethical practices.
- 2) Be sensitive to cultural differences. The literature generally mentions the relations with foreign partners, although it can apply the concept of organizational culture.
- 3) Recognize that collaboration should benefit all parties.
- 4) Ensure that commitments are met.
- 5) Structuring collaborative efforts to achieve the objectives without undermining the position of somewhere.
- 6) Structuring governance processes to ensure that decisions are taken swiftly when necessary.
- 7) Use learning to adjust the terms of cooperation to new internal and external circumstances.

All these skills and behaviors were mentioned in the model of rethinking leadership Bolman and Deal (Bolman & Deal, 2013). This model includes four frames of leadership: structural, human, political and symbolic resources. Particularly, skills to identify opportunities and design strategies (structural frame), and the trading and construction of coalitions (policy framework) are included by the authors as their own leadership. To apply these skills and behaviors to the formation of networks can be summarized that leadership is the key behavioral element.

5. Relationship of the behaviors and networks

Camarinha and Afsarmanesh (2011) showed the relationship of behavioral aspects of collaborative business networks. The paradigm of collaborative networks can empower companies with the agility and survivability to cope with the market turmoil. However, the success and sustainability of collaboration requires understanding and modeling the behavioral aspects involved, a basis for sound development support tools and mechanisms of good governance ... This includes the development, emotional health, incentives, conflicts of network preference and negotiation, the alignment of value systems, preparation for collaboration, and governance principles.

The main hypothesis is that understanding, modeling and reasoning about the behavior selected issues, while forming the basis for deriving the principles of fluids government, establish the basis for designing new tools and mechanisms to stimulate collaborative network behavior (Camarinha Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2011). Benito (2009) conducted a field study in microenterprises in Spain to know how the formation of enterprise networks contributes to regional development. The result of the study showed that less than half of respondents

think that networks are an efficient way to organize microenterprise, and less than 10% of respondents are part of a network.

The reason for this situation is the reluctance of employers due to lack of commitment and interest among members, the difficulty of reaching agreement because of the different interests of each party, ambition and human selfishness and the difficulties arising from the different features in the daily operations of each sector (Benito Hernandez, 2009). Barcellos et al. (2012) mention some aspects of derived individualism behavior, the divergence of objectives and lack of confidence conducive to the failure of alliances and networks (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Model of failure integrator alliances.
Source: Barcellos, Borella, Peretti and Galelli, 2012.

In their multi-case study, the authors found 12 reasons that led to the extinction of the analyzed networks: cultural aspects of each individual member (individualism, lack of commitment, resistance to change, lack of confidence, not sharing information), structural networks aspects (divergence of objectives, lack of leadership, size differences of the members, poor education, lack of preparation for participation in networks) and aspects of the culture of the network (relationship problems and expectation of fast results).

These factors demonstrate correspondence with the position of Gavetti (2012), in which the strategy was conceived and implemented in accordance with a behavioral model.

6. Discussion

Based on these processes a new model of the formation of business networks (Figure 23) is proposed.

Figure 23: Process networking formation.
Source: Authors.

To understand the dynamics of informal networks and their formalization, it starts from the vision that integrates the awareness of the driving forces and the benefits of integration. The second is the integration,

which involves selecting partners that will join the alliance, placing each node and its relationships in perspective using the concept of "role". A role is an organized set of behaviors that form a coherent whole if it refers to a specific goal and defines a certain position in the network where it interacts (Ramos, 2008, p. 70).

Society and organizations like the component parts are constituted by a set of roles linked each other among them. An organization is distinguished from an aggregate of individuals because there is an adaptation of individual behavior and because it takes place between all the feeling of being united to pursue and achieve goals together. Each of the existing roles in an organization has purpose in relation to others. Collaborate together to achieve the same goal and this collaboration comes from a sense of unity. The set of roles is cemented by the common mentality, or the same way of seeing things and consequently act of giving the same way in front of certain problems (Ramos, 2008, p. 71)

Once integrated into the network actors, it is necessary to make sense of identity. To do this, the definition of the objective and mission of the organization are key elements. The mission of the organization as "the *raison d'être*", can be understood as the main role of the company and its activities in relation to the society in which it develops and its needs, providing with it a sense of corporate identity. For the creation of an enterprise network, the definition of the common goal is the main element of cohesion to such an extent that if not, the development of network identity is not possible.

As time passes, all they co evolve in their capabilities and roles and tend to align with the directions proposed by one or more companies or influential pullers. Leadership roles in these companies change over time, and the community values the role of leader of the ecosystem, as this feature enables members to move towards a shared vision to align their investments and find mutually bearable roles (Mayenberger Scheel, 2008, p. 233).

As a fourth step, it is needed to establish the conditions for the operation, resulting in the establishment of rules of conduct or guidelines that serve as contractual terms in a formalization of the organization. This process may result in different levels of institutionalization, including the formation of new formal structures, such as joint ventures, strategic alliances agreements, among others. In other words, it must create the conditions for governance within the network (Giest & Howlett, 2014). Once the base of operations established, legally understood, planning is required. It must be established beyond the common long-term goals, short term goals and to implement specific cooperation activities and produce results. The evaluation results of short and long term goals become the main driver of the survival of the alliance.

Finally, based on the above arguments, it can be concluded that the enterprise networks evolve, and their structural characteristics (relations) depend on the behavior of the agents involved (Figure 24), from the identification of the driving forces or cognition, developing a shared vision (cognitive process) to the call, negotiation and execution of a network, then to take action to achieve results.

Figure 24 resulting model
Source: Authors

Therefore, the presence of collaborative behaviors promote cohesion and productive relations, while behaviors such as distrust, opportunism, among others, decrease cohesion, create conflicts and dissolve the network.

7. Conclusions

Enterprise networks represent a form of structure of industrial systems, drawn from the relationships between the actors, and formalized through various contractual means. Strategies companies are competitive in a level of performance in industrial systems, but can become collaborative in the presence of driving forces such as the threat of global players, actions of governments, among others.

Collaborative strategies are manifested through behavioral processes, such as the perception of the driving forces or cognitions and behaviors grouped in forms of leadership to create a vision and identity, convene and negotiate with competitors and complementing agents to formalize networks, such as alliances, clusters, among other structures. This phenomenon of collaboration between companies is particularly important for SME's; who may seek competitive advantages that otherwise might not develop. To achieve goals that require collaboration, the basic process of networking formation is applied in the pursuit of competitiveness of regions, tourist destinations, and industrial groupings.

Networking of SME's is equated with the formation of networks of business units of large companies, where the differences between these two structures are the identity and ownership, and the resulting challenges to governance. These factors result in the need for collaborative behavior of agents representing SME's in the process of formalization of the networks.

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